

[Biomarker Analytical Laboratories](#)

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Title: SOP for derivatisation of metabolite standards for analysis via GC Orbitrap

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Summary

Many compounds require derivatisation to be amenable for GC-MS analysis. Here a two-step oximation and trimethylsilylation procedure, commonly performed for metabolites, is described. Application to authentic standards enables collection of spectra required to generate spectral libraries necessary for automated compound identification and confirmation in samples.

Preparation

Safety information

- All work should be conducted in fume hood.
 - MeOx: Danger - corrosive, harmful, health hazard, environmental hazard
 - Pyridine: Danger - harmful, flammable
 - MSTFA: Warning - harmful, flammable

Equipment

- 10 uL , 100 uL & 5 mL pipettes
- Dry heat bath with aluminium blocks for 2 mL vials
- Centrifugal evaporator or N₂ evaporator
- Storage boxes for 2 mL vials
- Mini vortex
- Analytical balance (mg accuracy)

Consumables & glassware

- 2 mL screw cap glass autosampler vials with caps (PTFE septa) and 200 uL glass inserts
 - Need to make sure caps perfectly fit to prevent evaporation during derivatisation.
- 10 – 20 mL glass tube/ bottle with tight sealing screw cap
 - Caps must be airtight to store pyridine.
- 10 uL , 100 uL & 5 mL tips
- Labels for 2 mL vials

Reagents

- GC grade anhydrous pyridine >99 % purity
 - Pyridine will discolour to yellow if old or impure.
- Methoxyamine hydrochloride (MeOx) > 97.5 %
 - MeOx reacts with carbonyl groups (e.g. ketones, aldehydes) to form oxime and prevent numerous enol forms that gives rise to many peaks, especially for reducing sugars.
 - Optionally, MeOx reaction can be excluded for compounds without carbonyl group.
- *N*-methyl-*N*-(trimethylsilyl)trifluoroacetamide (MSTFA) > 98%
 - MSTFA replaces free hydroxyl groups with trimethylsilyl (TMS) to reduce polarity and increase volatility (alcohol > phenol > carboxylic acid > amine > amide).
 - Alternatively can use MSTFA + 1% trimethylchlorosilane (TMCS) as an extra catalyst if many sites observed to be unreacted. (Typically, does not make a difference when using pyridine).

MeOx solution (20 mg/mL in pyridine)

- For 5 mL of solution, weigh 100 mg methoxyamine hydrochloride into glass tube.
- Add 5 mL of pyridine and vortex until dissolved.
 - Solution can be kept for 3 days at room temp. Store double wrapped (e.g. parafilm cap and place glass tube in plastic falcon).

Procedure

Standards

- GC amendable standards requiring derivatisation should be prepared individually.
 - Individual compounds form numerous derivative products that need to be related to parent which makes compound mixtures inappropriate for library construction.
- Solvent choice for preparation of stocks is not crucial as extracts are subsequently dried. However, use the highest purity possible.
- To easily attain high-quality spectra on the Q Exactive GC Orbitrap it is best to load 50 – 500 pg on column. However, anywhere from ~5 – 100,000 pg is possible, depending on compound class.

Standard preparation

1. Label 2 mL glass autosampler vials containing 200 uL glass inserts.
2. Pipette 50 ng (e.g. 10 uL of 5 ug/ mL) of each GC standard into individual vial with insert.
3. Dry until complete dryness using a centrifugal evaporator or under N₂.

4. Store dry standards at -80 °C or -20 °C until further processing.

Derivatisation

5. Remove vials from freezer, decap and leave for 20 minutes in fume hood.
 - Moisture prevents derivatisation reaction.
6. Pre-heat dry heat block to 60 °C.
7. Add 30 uL MeOx solution to each standard and incubate at 60 °C for 1h.
8. Add 70 uL MSTFA and incubate at 60 °C for 1h.
9. Remove from heat block & place on ice for a couple of minutes.
10. Inject onto GC-MS system.
 - Derivatives should be injected within 24h. At most, derivatives can be injected within 48h if stored free from moisture at -20 °C.